

AUTOMATED HIGH VOLUME PRODUCTION OF COMPLEX COMPOSITES PARTS: CMTS (CONTINUOUS MULTI-TOW SHEARING)

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ABSTRACT

Automation is a highly sought-after property in composites manufacturing and especially in the aerospace industry. The demands of the industry, however, exceed the manufacturing capabilities of automated material placement machines. In particular, as the application of fibre placement technologies expanded to more complex parts, tow steering became one of the most critical capabilities. The steering process causes many different types of defects, and their minimisation has become a major issue. To eliminate such defects, a novel concept, Continuous Tow Shearing (CTS), was recently developed. In CTS, the tows are sheared continuously to steer the fibre path instead of inducing in-plane bending. One of the advantages of the CTS concept is that the material width does not affect the steering radius. In previous research, in order to fully exploit this feature, the concept of Continuous Multi Tow Shearing (CMTS) was developed, which employs unidirectional carbon fibre fabric with multiple tows and can significantly improve productivity. In this paper, the principle and technical aspects of this new automated manufacturing technology are outlined. A complete experimental simulator of the CMTS process is analysed and preliminary benchmarking results are presented and discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Automation

Automation is highly desired in nearly all production facilities, as it enhances performance and ultimately reduces costs. This is especially true for the aerospace industry, where quality standards are very high and there is a demand for increased production volumes. As future aircraft will have an ever-increasing number of composite parts, the focus is placed on the manufacturing processes for composite materials, in order to deliver high quality and improved productivity. To achieve this, a lot of attention has been placed on automated material placement machines [1].

The two prevailing technologies are Automated Tape Laying (ATL) and Automated Fibre Placement (AFP). In their essence both are the same, with their main differences found in the material format (wide and narrow tapes, respectively) and the deposition technique [1].

1.2 Tow Steering

Nowadays composites designers push for the introduction of increasingly complex parts into modern aircraft, in favour of optimised performance. The need was therefore created for the development of machines, which could lay-up on complex moulds. To maintain a constant fibre orientation on a mould with double curvature, the fibre paths have to be steered [2], making tow steering one of the key capabilities of modern day automated material placement machines. Tow steering also enables the manufacture of variable angle tow (VAT) panels, greatly expanding the design window for structural optimisation of composite parts. VAT panels exhibit improved buckling

and post-buckling performance, providing the potential to further reduce the weight of conventional composite aerospace components [3].

Improved steering capability is one of the primary needs, which requires the improvement of current AFP machines. As the automated placement machines employ in-plane bending of the tows, to steer the fibre path (by rotating the head in order to follow a curved trajectory), the width of the tow greatly affects the steering radius that can be achieved without the introduction of major defects. This radius is defined as the minimum steering radius and is approximately 6000 mm for ATL layup, using 150 mm wide tape [4], and 650 mm for AFP layup using 6.35 mm wide tow [5]. As the minimum steering radius is coupled with the width of the tape, by reducing the width, it was possible to develop improved steering capabilities. This is why AFP machines are designed to lay up simultaneously multiple narrow tows with widths ranging from 3.2mm to 12.7mm [1].

2 CONTINUOUS MULTI TOW SHEARING (CMTS)

Although improved fibre steering capabilities and higher production rates have been in much demand in recent years, the aerospace industry is attempting to tackle these requirements by employing the same concept that was introduced nearly four decades ago. The development of AFP has facilitated a reduction in the minimum steering radius. However, the coupling between the material width and the minimum steering radius remains as the primary problem. This is due to the fact that in-plane bending is employed to steer the fibre path, leading to fibre buckling (compression on one side of the tow and tension on the other) and extensive defects.

A novel concept was presented in Ref. [6], called Continuous Tow Shearing (CTS), in which material shear deformation is employed in order to steer the fibre path. It is reported that a minimum steering radius nearly 10 times lower than that of AFP can be achieved. It is also stated, however, that the material deposition rate is fairly slow, due to the fact that a resin tape has to be heated and impregnate a dry tow prior to deposition, which could limit the industrial uptake of this concept. Nevertheless, one of the most important advantages of this concept is the fact that due to the employment of shear deformation, the coupling between material width and minimum steering radius is broken.

To address the productivity issue, the concept of Continuous Multi Tow Shearing (CMTS) was presented in Ref. [7], where the same shearing mechanism is employed, while using multiple tows, in the form of a wide dry tape. In this paper, a complete prototype is developed for the CMTS technology in order to benchmark its performance and compare figures such as layup accuracy and defect minimisation with those of the CTS, which lays up a single tow.

2.1 Prototype development

The experimental simulator developed in this project, is comprised of a 4-axis CNC gantry and a laboratory scale CMTS head. The CMTS head can lay-up carbon tape and resin tape of up to 100 mm width (Figure 1). For the experiment presented in this paper, a unidirectional carbon fabric tape with a width of 100 mm comprising 40 24K tows and weft yarns across the width was employed. A 125 gsm B-staged epoxy resin film (914, Hexcel, USA) was used. Concerning the direction of movement of the materials (Figure 2), the carbon fabric and resin tape come in contact as they enter the compaction rollers. As the tapes pass through the rollers, the pressure gradually increases causing the resin to be transferred to the bottom surface of the carbon fabric. After the compaction stage, the carbon fabric tape reaches the pinch device. The carbon fabric with the transferred resin film on its bottom, which is separated from the backing paper, is fed into the compaction shoe as the head moves. The release paper is driven by the take-up rollers and is wound on the release paper creel as shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 1: CMTS Lab scale prototype head.

The CMTS has two additional stages to the lay-up process compared to ATL and AFP, the compaction stage and the shearing stage (Figure 1). During the compaction stage, the resin is only deposited to the fibres, without achieving full impregnation. Therefore, contrary to the CTS process, there is no need to heat the resin, to reduce its viscosity, allowing faster lay-up speeds. During the shearing stage, the compaction shoe presses and secures the tows at the immediately previous position of the head. The pinch device holds the carbon fabric tape at the current position of the head. The lateral difference of the two positions causes the shearing of the tows (Figure 2). Therefore the CMTS head, contrary to the AFP and ATL, does not rotate to steer the fibre path.

The feeding mechanism of CMTS is active, compared to ATL and AFP, where it is passive. The whole tape dispensing system in CMTS is powered by a DC motor which drives the two paper take-up rollers. Without an active feeding system, it is not possible to shear the fibres, as the relative movement of the head can cause the tape to be straightened and subsequently bent. The second reason is that the tension, which is required to drag the tape through the resin compaction mechanism and the pinch device, is greater than the force that the already laid-up tape can sustain before it starts to debond.

To maximize the uniformity of the pressure distribution on the compaction shoe surface and increase overall modularity, the head was separated into a layup unit and a creel unit (Figure 2). To increase the overall robustness, two guided pneumatic cylinders were employed. Furthermore the creel unit, which is the heaviest component of the head due to the material weight, was bolted directly to the fixed body of the pneumatic pistons, so as not to affect the pressure distribution at the compaction shoe.

To monitor and regulate the feed speed of the carbon fabric tape, a dual loop speed control was implemented. The main encoder is attached to one of the compaction rollers (Figure 2), while the auxiliary encoder is attached to the motor shaft. Actual tape feeding speed is different from the value calculated from the rotation speed of the motor, due to the flexibility of the silicone rollers, the extension of the backing paper under tension, and a certain degree of backlash of the motor gearbox.

To address this issue, the main encoder was placed as near to the lay-up point as possible, to give an accurate value of the feed speed. Finally the material feed speed was synchronised with the head moving speed.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2: Schematics of the CMTS prototype head and shearing mechanism: (a) material flow within the head, (b) shear deformation within the shearing gap.

The head was mounted on a moving part of a CNC gantry machine with 4 degrees of freedom: 3 linear (X, Y, Z) and one rotational (along Z). In order to simulate the CMTS process, 2 linear axes (X, Y) were used and the rotational axis was used only to change the reference angle at the beginning of each course.

3 MANUFACTURING CHARACTERISTICS

3.1 EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

The reasoning behind the development of the CMTS simulator is to benchmark the performance of the process. The derived data will be useful in order to improve the functioning of the head itself and in order to identify the materials (resin film and fabric) that can deliver the optimal performance. In this paper only preliminary results and observations are presented.

In the presented experiment, a fixed steering radius of 300 mm was chosen for the steered fibre path. The maximum reference fibre angle was 27° and the steered horizontal length of the path was 290 mm in total (Figure 3). The material feed and head moving speed was 4 mm/s. The aluminium substrate was covered by a 0.1 mm thick self-adhesive vinyl film and the tape was laid up on top of it.

Figure 3: Geometric features of the specimen that was produced.

After the layup of the specimen using the CMTS simulator, the top surface of the specimen was scanned using a high resolution scanner (EPSON Expression 11000xl) at 1200 dpi. When the specimen was scanned with the fibre path vertical to the scanner light source, the derived image was of poor quality and it was difficult to determine the individual tows (Figure 4). This is due to the fact that in this orientation only the diffuse reflection at the surface of the carbon fibres is captured, which is of low intensity, resulting in black carbon fibres. In general, the reflective diagram for carbon fibres is comprised of a diffuse and a reflective part [8]. In order to make the carbon fibre clearly visible, a specific angle among the fibre direction, the light source and the camera is required, in order to capture the reflective part [9].

Figure 4: Specimen produced with the CMTS Simulator. The image was scanned with the fibre orientation of the straight segments vertical to the light source and optical sensor of the scanner. As it can be seen from the magnified box, the quality is not adequate to accurately distinguish the tow boundaries.

As the fibre angle was not constant, 4 scans were taken to make the fibres in a certain area of the specimen visible, by aligning the fibre angle at an approximately parallel position with the light source

and optical sensor of the scanner. The images were then stitched together, using imaging software. To facilitate the stitching process, several printed rulers were placed on the specimen plate, in order to offer distinguishable common areas between the 4 individual scans. The resulting image can be seen in Figure 5. Once the specimen was adequately captured, an image analysis process followed, in order to quantify the main performance benchmarks for the specimen. In Figure 5, the solid lines depict the tape boundaries, while the dashed lines refer to the reference path. The deviation of the actual path from the reference path is the path error.

Figure 5: Stitched specimen images. In the magnified box it can be seen that the edges of the tows are adequately captured using this analysis.

3.2 RESULTS

As shown Figure 5, the actual path of the tape has some error compared to the reference path that was programmed into the CNC machine's coordinates. This was expected since the shearing gap, between the front end of the pinch device and the rear end of the compaction shoe, was approximately 3.5 mm at an angle of 45 degrees, which was much greater than that of the single tow layup CTS head [6, 7]. The programmed machine path is matched by the position where the tape is gripped at the pinch device. However, the tape that is pressed onto the mould is under the compaction shoe that is apart from the pinch device (by the 3.5 mm shearing gap), which creates an error on the actual tape path. In order to improve the accuracy of the process, an algorithm which compensates for this effect is required.

The fact that there is an error in the tape trajectory can be seen also on Figure 6, which represents the average fibre angle variation at the length of the specimen. The fibre angle was calculated at each of the tape boundaries at 1 mm intervals and then the two values were averaged to derive the average shear angle. The tape boundaries were smoothed in order to eliminate any noise, however the average shear angle still fluctuates, something which is attributed to localised wrinkles. From Figure 6, it was found that except the region near the inflection point the angle error was within $\pm 2^\circ$. However, near the inflection point the error was considerable, which was the same trend with the previous test results, using the single tow layup CTS head [10].

Figure 6: Average Shear angle of the tape boundaries at each position of the tape.

Furthermore, the shift width (Figure 7) was calculated as the distance between two points on the tape boundaries with the same x-coordinate (Figure 3). The nominal tape width in the creel was 100 mm, however it was compressed to 89 mm by employing two roller guides, in order to eliminate the pre-existing gaps between the tows. The shift width should theoretically remain constant during steering, as individual fibres can reposition themselves within the tow as the shear angle increases [6]. In Figure 7, the average and the actual shift widths are plotted at 1 mm intervals. The average shift width is approximately 89.4 mm which is slightly higher than the one expected. The shift width also fluctuates in the range of 89 – 90 mm. This is because the alignment of the carbon fibres with the resin tape and also the accuracy of the roller guides was not optimal.

Figure 7: Shift width at each position of the tape.

In order to investigate the development of resin gaps between the tows, the tape image was separated into 3 segments (Figure 8). Each of these segments was further separated into smaller segments, by employing two vertical guide lines 15 mm apart. The resin gap area was selected and its pixel number was divided with the pixel number of the fabric contained in the segment, to derive the percentage of the area occupied by resin pockets (Figure 9). It becomes evident that the segment of the

tow which is close to the upper boundary (Tows 31-40) has a significantly reduced overall resin pocket area compared to the two other segments.

Figure 8: Gap generation in the sheared unidirectional carbon fabric using CMTS.

(The magnified areas represent the parts with the largest resin pockets. The resin gaps, were colored red, due to the resin itself, however they have been changed to white color in this figure, in order to make them distinguishable.)

The main difference between this segment and the rest is the tension of the weft yarns. The upper segment has maintained a much more coherent structure, with almost equal spacing between the adjacent weft yarns. The width of the tows on that segment also appears to be significantly smaller compared to the rest of the tows. This is probably related to the original configuration and fabrication method of the material, which has a one-sided stitch selvedge. In this configuration, if the weft yarn is tensioned during the material manufacturing process, then as it is wound over the tows at the edge, it squeezes the tow bundle reducing its width. To further investigate this assumption, a straight path lay up was performed (Figure 10), where the same tow structure can be observed, meaning that the particular gap generation pattern is probably not related with the shearing deformation of the material. Another possible reason, is that the weft yarns in the middle segment (Tows 11-30) appear to be dragged by the edge of the compaction shoe (Figure 8), something which would increase the tension in the other two segments, as the weft yarn is fixed on the edges of the tape. The tow width variation within the material also causes the thickness variation along the material width, which can affect the evenness of the compaction pressure during the layup. This highlights the importance of the weaving pattern of the weft yarn for the reduction of defects during the CMTS operation.

Figure 9: Estimation of resin pocket area percentage through image analysis.

Figure 10: Segment of the UD fabric material from a straight path lay up. The red tow borderlines highlight the difference between the tow widths at different areas.

4 CONCLUSION

In this paper, the operation and design of a complete simulator for the CMTS process, which can lay up a wide unidirectional carbon fabric tape comprising 40 24K tows, was presented. In order to evaluate its layup quality, an image analysis method, which can capture the tow boundaries of the laid tape and extract their geometrical features, was outlined. This methodology was necessary to benchmark its performance and capabilities, in order to study the process parameters affecting the quality and further develop this technology. The results from a preliminary experiment were analysed and investigated. Although several more experiments have to be performed in order to draw any clear conclusions, some useful observations can be made.

The error between the reference and the actual path was considerable compared to when the single tow layup head was used, which is probably attributed to the larger shearing gap between the pinch device and the compaction shoe. A machine control algorithm that can compensate for this error needs to be developed. Furthermore it is highly probable that the weft yarn pattern and tension has an effect on the shearing performance. Tensioned weft yarn in the unidirectional carbon fabric significantly reduced resin pockets. Other fabrics with different weave patterns and materials have to be examined and experimented with at this stage, in order to unravel the effect of the weft yarn properties on the shearing and defect generation characteristics of the fabric materials.

Despite the path error, it was shown that a steering radius of 300 mm for a 100 mm tape (compressed to 89 mm) can be achieved. This steering radius is an order of magnitude lower than the one achieved by modern ATL machines for the same width of tape.

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